

Spatial Practices in Art and Architecture
for Empathetic EXchange (SPACEX)

Mid-Term Meeting Report

Work Package 1 Project Management
and Training

Andy Hewitt & Mel Jordan

Version 1.0

Deliverable description

Deliverable

D2 Work Package 1: Project Management and Training (WP 1)
D1.2 Mid-Term Meeting Report (MTMR)

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Work Package concerned

WP 1 – Project Management and Training

Work package leader

Prof. Andrew Hewitt, (University of Northampton)

Dissemination level

- PU: Public (must be available on the website)
 CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Statement of originality

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Disclaimer

This report reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Abstract

The mid-term meeting report discusses the activities undertaken in the first 18 months of Spatial Practices in Art and Architecture for Empathetic Exchange (SPACEX-RISE) project and considers the coming networking activities up to the end of the first period (January 2024). All the actions have fully achieved the objectives of the period. Eighty-six researchers have been involved in network and training activities. 21 secondments have been completed. According to the updated mobility plan for the end of the first period, an additional 45 of the total 132 PMs will be in progress, in line with SPACEX-RISE targets.

SPACEX Beneficiaries

SHORTNAME	Cultural Organisations
RESERVA	A Reserva na Fábrica, Oeiras, Portugal
AA&U	Architecture, Art and Urbanism, Nicosia, Cyprus
CB	Coventry Biennial, Coventry, UK
FEST	Festival dei Popoli, Florence, Italy
CASCO	Foundation Casco, Utrecht, NL
H4C	Home for Cooperation (H4C), Nicosia, Cyprus
L40	Kunstverein am Rosa-Luxemburg-Platz, Berlin, Germany
LUC	Laboratory for Urban Commons, Athens, Greece
NN	NN Contemporary, Northampton, UK
MDAY	Mayday Rooms, London, UK
PAC	Project Arts Centre, Dublin, Ireland
PCG	Prague City Gallery, Czech Republic
SAC	Sirius, Cork, Ireland
STROOM	Stroom Den Haag, The Netherlands
TRANS	transparadiso, Vienna, Austria
VANABBE	Van Abbemuseum, Eindhoven NL
	Higher Education Institutes (HEI's)
AVUP	Academy of Fine Arts, Prague, Czech Republic
CU	Coventry University, UK
NCAD	National College of Art & Design, Dublin, Ireland
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens, Greece
RCA	Royal College of Art, London UK
UVA	University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands
UVAA	University of Applied Arts, Vienna, Austria
UNIARTS	University of the Arts, Helsinki, Finland
UCD	University College Dublin, Ireland
UCY	University of Cyprus, Cyprus
UNIMORE	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
UON	University of Northampton, UK
	Third Country Partner
WC	Wonder Cabinet

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Definitions and Acronyms

DCOP	Dissemination Communication and Outreach Plan
DECE	Dissemination and Exploitation: Communication and Engagement
EC	European Commission
EDI	Equality, Diversity & Inclusion
GA	Grant Agreement
GAS	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
Metadata	A description of data
MTMR	Mid Term Meeting Report
MSCA	<i>Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions</i>
PM	Person Month 31 days secondment period
Practice Research	SPACEX-RISE is a practice research project. Some research will culminate in artworks. Artworks are designed to be shared publicly through exhibition or dissemination on the website.
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RT	Research Topics
RISE	Research and Innovation Staff Exchange
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SPACEX - RISE	Spatial Practices in Art and Architecture for Empathetic Exchange Research and Innovation Staff Exchange
SB	Steering Board
TE	Training Event. (SPACEX has 4 Training Events)
WP1 – WP5	Work Packages

Table 2: Definitions and Acronyms

1. Introduction

Prof. Andrew Hewitt

The Mid-Term Meeting Report (MTMR) reviews the activities undertaken in the first 18 months of SPACEX- RISE project (March 2022 – January 2024) and considers the coming secondment activities, and research outputs up to the end of the next period (February 2024 – December 2025). The MTMR is the Deliverable D2.1 (D2) from the Project Management Work Package, SPACEX project - grant agreement (GA 872561).

The MTMR is an information tool for the MTM event on 20 September 2023. The event is a hybrid event, however not all PIs are able to attend, therefore we have produced a printed (PDF) document to capture actions to date. This will allow the report contents to be distributed before the MTM event, so all PIs have access to the material. There are contributions from PIs in relation to secondments and training events, these are noted in the booklet, and they will be spoken to at the event. There will be an appendix addition to this report after the Mid Term Meeting is held on 20 September 2023, and the MTMR (version 1.1) will be distributed to all SPACEX-RISE beneficiaries by 31 October 2023 and published on the website.

Actions to address all SPACEX- RISE objectives for this period of activity have begun. The SPACEX -RISE project allocated 132 PMs of its awarded 150 PMs. 86 researchers are confirmed to undertake at least 1 Person Month. 27 researchers have contributed to training events. 60 researchers have attended the first three Training Events. 8 researchers have contributed to online seminars. 40 Person Months are in progress. 21 Person Months have been completed by September 2023. Our forecast is that 50% of the total number of secondments will be completed or in progress by the end of the first period (January 2024), in line with project expectations.

The MTMR reviews the project to date. Short progress reports from WP 1- WP5 are included as well as reports from secondments and three completed Training Events.

The MTMR provides project information for all PI's and operates as a SPACEX-RISE update reporting mechanism.

1.1. Project Background

The SPACEX-RISE project is funded by the European Commission under its 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) programme. In SPACEX-RISE 28 beneficiaries, (16 Cultural organisations and 12 HEI's) in European regions and one third country partner (Palestine, cultural organisation). In total 29 partner institutions set out to consider how spatial practices (art, design, and architecture) effect public exchange and opinion formation in urban spaces and promote empathetic and inclusive ways of living together. The aim of SPACEX-RISE is to realise a cross-sectoral and European-wide knowledge exchange and scoping exercise.

SPACEX- RISE responds to the troubling rise of populist nationalism and conflict in European societies by engaging new publics and forging a culture that embraces diversity, difference, and discursive exchange within cities, towns, and urban sites.

In response to the RISE programme, we devised SPACEX-RISE as a transdisciplinary research action that utilises secondments between academic institutions and third sector organisations/ cultural organisation to better understand the scope and function of European spatial practices. Furthermore, SPACEX-RISE is the first European consortium of Spatial Practices.

Currently there are 86 researchers carrying out at least one secondment as part of the project. SPACEX-RISE has allocated funding for 132 PMs. For Higher Education Institutions (HEI's) outputs will be varied but include, book chapters, new artworks, journal articles and impact reports. For cultural organisations outputs will include evaluation strategies, events, exhibitions, and reports.

1.2 Work Package 1: Project Management

There are no secondments associated with WP1. Table 3 shows the status of deliverables and the milestones completed in the first 18 months of the project. There are no delays accumulated in research activities and deliverables. The aim of WP1 is to, i) create an effective communication among beneficiaries and to external agents, ii) monitor the project plan and progress, iii) compile reports and reporting to REA, iv) manage financial and legal issues of the project. The key deliverables for the first period are D1.1 D1 First Progress Report, and D1.2 D2 Mid Term Meeting, which are now complete.

WP1	D1.1	D1	First Progress Report
WP1	D1.2	D2	Mid Term Meeting
WP5	D5.1	D13	Communication, Dissemination & Outreach Plan (DCOP) and Data Management Plan (DMP)
WP5	D5.2	D14	Graphic Design and Website
WP5	D5.3	D15	Outreach Events organisation and delivery M6, 12,15,18
WP5	D5.6	D18	Guest Edited Journal Issue
WP6	D6.1	D19	H - Requirement No. 6
WP6	D6.2	D20	POPD - Requirement No. 10

Table.3 SPACEX deliverable for WP1, WP5, WP6.

The WP1 has fully achieved the objectives for the period. Details of those actions as well as general management tasks and activity undertaken in this period are reported below, as are the deliverables for WP5 and WP6.

1.3 Kick-off meeting

The Kick-off meeting was hosted online at Coventry University, on 3 February 2022 using the Zoom Platform to reach all PIs. The Kick-Off meeting was the first opportunity to discuss the project activities with all the PIs and for them to meet the REA Aleksandra Schoetz-Sobczak.

1.4 Overall Coordination

All the activities for a good coordination of the project have been undertaken. The overall coordination of financial and administrative aspects was ensured.

General Assemblies and have been held regularly. All meetings have been on online, the first GAS was held on the 10 May 2022, followed by meetings on 5 July 2022, 1 November 2022, 10 January 2023, 9 May 2023, 12 September 2023, with the seventh meeting planned for 5 December 2023. The main function of the GAS is to ensure that the secondments are progressing according to the plan agreed in the Grant Agreement. This allows us to address any ethical, legal and gender issues relevant to the project should they arise, to approve project budgets associated with the networking activities and to resolve any conflict between the PC and any participant. In addition, we can address any IPR issues relevant to the project should those arise. Importantly, the GAS is a meeting point for all PIs to discuss and clarify their understanding of the project and its operations so that they in turn can cascade the information to the researchers in their institution and to colleagues in research

management or institutional governance. As such, in the absence of face-to-face meetings, largely due to our geographic distance and exacerbated by Covid, the GAS have been the main means of communication for the consortium in learning how to work together to conduct the research action.

Minutes about our discussions and subsequent list of actions are circulated among all partners after the meeting and are then uploaded in the shared folder. The GAS provided the opportunity to check the work in progress, the achievement of main results and manage possible risks and difficulties. A repository with all the key documents has been created. All partners have access to it. Administrative support has been provided by Kauser Hussain (CU) and since August 2023 by Marley Treloar (CU).

All the activities for a good overall coordination of the project have been undertaken. The coordination of financial and administrative aspects was ensured. The distribution of financial resources to the beneficiaries was made in accordance with the procedures reported in the Consortia Agreement. The Consortia Agreement (DESCA) has been agreed by all beneficiaries. Management tasks included processing the payment of monies to beneficiaries and was managed at UON. The first instalments for all 28 beneficiaries were met following the payment policy of UON, in arranging transfers via the university finance department. Payments were made promptly once beneficiaries had completed the necessary university procurement documents. Sums varied according to the number of person months agreed by the beneficiary. First payments for HEI partners were 40% of the allocation, with cultural partners on 60% as agreed in the GAS. This was to ensure that smaller cultural partners often operating on limited budgets had the necessary funds to enable researchers to finance their secondment.

1.5 Monitoring

Regular communications between beneficiaries were held through emails, online meeting, and news in the website areas. The GAS have been the main opportunity to monitor the project activities. A survey was conducted as an additional monitoring process, to provide data on the researcher's backgrounds.

Figure 1: Count of Gender: Female 56. Male 30

Figure 2: Secondment Distribution: ER's 47, ESR's 39

Figure 3: SPACEX Beneficiaries

Figure 4: Researchers by Nationality

During the first reporting period, secondments have been taking place. SPACEX-RISE has allocated 132 person months for over 86 researchers, across 28 beneficiaries. Currently we have 21 person months (PM) completed which is 16% of the overall number of PM. 33 secondments are underway with person month's part completed and plans in place for the remaining days. 59 secondments are due to begin either between now and the end of the first phase in January 2024 or into the second phase of the action ending in the second half of 2025.

As a result of COVID 19 pandemic the take up of secondments has been slower than expected. This was due in part to policy by nation states to restrict travel to contain the spread of COVID 19 and which continued to impinge on the take up secondments even as the threat from Covid diminished. Hence, as we restarted SPACEX-RISE in March 2020 there were dampers on our capacity to begin the research action. Researchers' ability to travel was to some degree hindered by new forms of institutional or governmental clearance for travel, the restart for travel operators was gradual, and HEI and cultural organisations were faced with prioritising their core operational activity ahead of research development. Consequently, the take up and completion of secondments in the first period was initially slow. Those days are now behind us and there is clear evidence that research secondments are underway, and the research activity in the network is developing momentum.

STATUS OF SECONDMENTS SEPTEMBER 2023 (20 MONTHS)

Figure 5: Status of Secondments September 2023: Completed 21, In Progress 40, In Planning 71

Figure 6: WP2 36, WP3 34, WP4 16

Figure 7: Completed 10, In Progress 17, In Planning 25

Figure 8: Completed 7, In Progress 11, In Planning 31

Figure 9: Completed 4, In Progress 11, In Planning 16

1.6 Ethics

Ethical considerations are an ongoing process, and researchers are reminded to continually assess and address ethical issues as the SPACEX-RISE project progresses. Each secondment has a specific nature, led by the researcher undertaking the secondment. Cultural institutions host events and support visitors to their galleries and exhibitions therefore they have everyday health and safety regulations in place. The project includes a range of approaches to research during secondments, from desk work, archival research, to artistic works made for exhibition. The ethical risks levels for this work are typically low with occasional instances of mid-range outcomes. Those risks will be in the use of data, reproduction of existing materials, the making of new research with people. Aspects of the action are practice research which usually result in interventions into public spaces, for example a hosted public talk. The visitors to talks are understood as audiences rather than

participants. However, in some, cases (WP2 & WP3) researchers may develop a participatory project or event where members of the public / or community aligned to the cultural organisation, are asked to give their views or opinions, in these instances ethics approval are needed and should be sought from the researcher's institution as well as the Ethics Review Team (SERT).

Information for Ethics is contained in the Grant Agreement, Appendix 1, 'SPACE X Information for Research Participants,' pg 39 – 54.

1.6.1 Ethics Summary Issues for Consideration

The guiding principles of the SPACE X -RISE ethics policy is for non-maleficence and beneficence, indicating a systematic regard for the rights and interests of others in the full range of academic relationships and activities.

In summary the issues that need to be considered:

- i. **Informed Consent:** Researchers must ensure that all participants in the project provide informed consent before participating. This includes clear explanations of the project's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants should have the freedom to withdraw from the project at any time.
- ii. **Privacy and Data Protection:** Protecting the privacy of participants and their personal data is crucial. Researchers should adhere to data protection regulations and implement appropriate measures to secure sensitive information.
- iii. **Conflicts of Interest:** Researchers involved in the project should disclose and potential conflicts of interest that could affect the integrity of the research outcomes.
- iv. **Benefits Sharing:** If the project involves collaboration with participants or communities' consideration should be given to how to share knowledge and resources in an equitable manner.
- v. **Open Access and Knowledge Sharing:** Ethical considerations related to the dissemination of project outcomes, including sharing research findings and data, should be addressed to ensure transparency and accessibility.
- vi. **Societal Impact:** The project's potential impact on society, both positive and negative, should be carefully assessed and addressed. This includes considerations of fairness, inclusivity, and potential unintended consequences.
- vii. **Environmental Impact:** If the project involves activities that could have an impact on the environment, measures should be taken to minimize any negative effects and promote sustainability.

- viii. **Responsible Innovation:** Researchers should engage in responsible innovation practices, considering the broader implications of their work and involving stakeholders in discussions about potential ethical concerns.

Figure 10: Introduction to Ethics accessed [here](#)

1.7 Corrective Measures

Planning for activities and deliverables has been generally successful as outlined above. However, we had to apply for force majeure due to the COVID 19 Pandemic, when all country's participating went into lockdown. In the context of a project like RISE (Research and Innovation Staff Exchange European Union) which promotes research collaboration and knowledge exchange among institutions, the term "suspension under force majeure" refers to a situation where the project activities are temporarily halted or put on hold due to unforeseen and extraordinary circumstances that are beyond the control of the parties involved. This resulted in a suspension of the SPACEX- RISE action.

We began the SPACEX-RISE project in January 2020 and had to suspend it from March 2020 – January 2022. The SPACEX-RISE Project was granted an extended timeline beginning in March 2022 and ending in December 2025.

The SPACEX-RISE project was affected by:

- **Suspension and Delay:** The project activities were suspended and delayed. This involved a pause in research exchanges, collaborations, and other planned public activities. Unfortunately, we lost four beneficiaries during this time. For example, the Tate London were forced to withdraw from the project due to restructuring and a change in operational focus as a direct consequence of the period of closure and its

impact on funding. Economic and organisational issues were also to impact upon Threshold Studios, Publics Helsinki, and Athens Biennial who all sadly had to leave the project. To mitigate this situation, the SPACEX-RISE steering committee reached out to new organisations that would bring new interests and appropriate experience to the network. MayDay Rooms, Reserva Na Fabrica, Prague Art Gallery, Prague Academy of Fine Arts and Sirius Arts Centre joined the project. New beneficiaries took on the task of signing the GA on the EU portal, which was new to some and not easy for most. The process and mechanisms of the EU take some learning and it took some time before we had brought all new beneficiaries up to speed on the project aims and objectives and completed the sign-up to the GA.

The project action resumed in March 2022, but we recognised how our 16 cultural organisations were under more pressure than ever to maintain their activities within a field that was experiencing further cuts to spending and a greater demand on staff to fund raise. Those immense pressures continue, and we are aware of how challenging this is, and that this can and does impact on beneficiaries' ability to take on secondments. There are corresponding challenges in HEI sector, where academics have been forced to adapt working practices, for example, the immediate shift to online teaching, all of which has created pressure and extra workload for academics who do research.

- **Communication and Online events:** The online Kick-Off Meeting meant that we did not have the opportunity to meet face to face, this impacted upon our communications towards secondment organisations. The cost of the Kick-Off meeting was minimal which has been beneficial to the project finances. The PC and WP leaders created opportunities for online engagement, in the form of seminars and meetings. D5.6, D18 Guest Edited Journal was brought forward. Art and the Public Sphere Journal issue enabled researchers to contribute to a group project and interact with each other. To compensate for not being able to organise secondments and the suspension of the project researchers worked together to publish new work. Ten journal articles by nine researchers were completed. The authors included researchers from beneficiaries, Coventry University, National Technical University of Athens, National College of Art and Design, Dublin, Transparadiso, University of Vienna, Royal College of Art, as well as other contributors.

Figure 11: Art and Public Sphere Journal, Volume 9 Numbers 1 & 2, published December 2020. The open access articles are available at [here](#).

- **Resumption of Activities:** When the project resumed, travel restrictions were still in place and guidelines for travel were updated by HEI's. For example, Coventry University required permission from the Vice Chancellor to travel overseas. Cultural organisations took longer to get back to pre-COVID 19 work patterns, due to (in a lot of cases) preparing to reopen to the public. To mitigate these issues the Steering Committee adopted a flexible and proactive approach to navigate challenges posed by the pandemic to maintain the project objectives. Priority was given to the safety and well-being of all project participants by following guidelines and recommendations for health authorities and governments. This involved embracing remote collaboration tools and technologies to facilitate virtual communication and collaboration among project partners including virtual meetings, video conference and using online collaboration platforms. The PC adapted project timelines and developed new ways to collaborate. The benefits of this were that the project team were encouraged towards a collaborative and problem-solving mindset to address challenges and find innovative solutions.
- **Brexit**, which refers to the United Kingdom's decision to leave the European Union (EU), has impacted upon the project. This raised issues regarding Data sharing and data protection regulations between the UK and the EU following Brexit. It affected our existing GA contract, as raised with the National Technical University of Athens. There was discussion regarding Data sharing and data protection regulations between the UK and the EU following Brexit. This required consideration of how data is collected, stored, and shared among project partners. This impacted upon the delivery of the Data Management Plan (DMP) and the Dissemination,

Communication and Outreach Plan (DCOP) as they are a combined deliverable, D5.1, D13.

1.8 Potential Risks and Mitigation

SPACEX-RISE PC, WP Leaders and the Steering Committee have applied a Risk Management approach that involves proactive planning, careful management, and ongoing monitoring to minimize the impact of potential challenges. A 12-point plan is followed that includes: Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Planning, Communication and Collaboration, Contingency Planning, Budget Allocation, Risk Monitoring, Adaptability and Flexibility, Stake Holder Engagement, Training and Skill Development, Documentation, and Review and Learning.

- **Regulatory and Compliance Risks:** Changes in regulations, laws, or policies in participating countries could affect the project's activities, particularly in areas such as data privacy, intellectual property rights, ethics and work permits for staff mobility. To mitigate for this, we have delayed the completion of the DMP to ensure that Brexit does not impact the GDPR. Currently staff mobility from some UK HEI's requires a business plan and this is initiated by Human Resources for compliance purposes, UK researchers are asked to complete this as part of the administrative processes of the project.
- **Partner Incompatibility:** Misalignment in goals, expectations, or work approaches among project partners can lead to communication challenges and impact upon secondment uptake. To mitigate this the PC (Hewitt) and WP2 & WP5 Leader (Jordan) are in constant contact with partners. Not all PIs have been able to support the co-ordination of researchers and their secondment as much as was expected. The next period will mean a vigorous attempt to organise secondments. Flexibility with secondment placement has addressed three of the issues arising regarding partner incompatibility.
- **Communication and Cultural Challenges:** The development of a 'Ethnicity, Diversity and Inclusion Plan' has created some concern across partners. Most beneficiaries are familiar with the need for a plan and value its function for analysing and reporting differences amongst groups of people. The plan has met with resistance and needs to be debated more carefully. To mitigate this the Steering Committee has sought advice and developed a 'working action plan'.

The research science in the project is concerned with diversity issues, and will employ decolonization theory, feminist theory, and intersectionality, this needs to be reflected in the structure of our management processes including our EDI plan. Sustainable issues within the project will be addressed through a Sustainability Statement. As a consortium we can choose to use the least polluting ways to travel, however this is usually more expensive. Some researchers have been able to travel by train particularly those in central Europe. In the consortium we have researchers who are concerned with sustainable cities, sustainable materials, and sustainable architecture, so we see the need to reflect on how to produce our research and what measures we can take to reduce impact on the environment. This is currently being developed and data is being collected.

- **Health and Safety Risks:** have already occurred regarding COVID 19 and the project team applied for a suspension via force majeure.
- **Uncertain Project Duration:** Unexpected extensions or delays in the project timeline. The project was resumed after COVID 19 lockdown was lifted but this still had an impact for partners response times, as all beneficiaries were addressing challenges that COVID 19 had caused. To mitigate communication has been made more open and researchers have been encouraged to attend as many Training Events as possible, with some ESR's staying with friends to keep their costs low so they could meet other researchers and organise secondments in person.
- **Budgeting:** There has been concern over rising inflation and the cost-of-living crisis impacting on our costs when travelling on secondment. While beneficiaries are made aware that the €2100 per person month is a 'top-up' amount, the funds in most cases do not adequately cover the full 31 days. Sixteen beneficiaries are cultural organisations, that are generally reliant on public funding. Allowing core staff to take secondments is costly for them and their operations, as well as the costly for researchers when away from home. UK HEI's compliance rules do not allow the researchers to receive the €2100 directly – leaving researchers having to use UK HEI's procurement processes for travel and accommodation, which usually means expensive outlays. To mitigate these issues shared accommodation has been offered with individual researchers donating free accommodation to the project. Cultural organisations with artist accommodation have offered support, e.g. SIRIUS, Rosa Luxemburg and Stroom. HEI researchers who are providing accommodation are UON and Coventry University.

1.9 Future Implementation

In the second phase of the action, we are programming regular meetings. This is to enable contact between researchers in and across work packages to share knowledge.

1.9.1 List of Ongoing and Future Deliverables

Deliverables, Ethics, DMP, Other Reports

WP No	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Nature	Est. Del. Date (annex I)	Status
WP1	Second Progress Report	UoN	Report	31 Jan 2023	Pending
WP2	Best practice report	UoN	Report	31 Jan 2025	Pending
WP2	SPACE X Fact Information sheet 1 for wider public access	CU	Report	31 Oct 2024	Pending
WP2	Spatial Practice Artworks 1	CU	Report	31 Dec 2024	Pending
WP3	Best practice report	CU	Other	30 Jun 2024	Pending
WP3	SPACE X Fact Information sheet no. 2 for wider public access	UCY	Report	31 Oct 2024	Pending
WP3	Spatial Practice Artworks 2	UCY	Report	31 Dec 2024	Pending
WP4	Best practice report:	UCY	Other	30 Jun 2024	Pending
WP4	SPACE X Fact Information sheet no. 3 for wider public access	NCAD	Report	31 Oct 2024	Pending
WP4	Spatial Practice Artworks 3	NCAD	Report	31 Dec 2024	Pending
WP5	DCOP and (DMP	NCAD	Other	30 Jun 2024	Pending
WP5	Graphic Design and Website	CU/ NCAD	ORDP: Open Rese	30 Jun 2022	Pending
WP5	Outreach Events organisation and delivery	CU/NCAD	Websites, patents f	31 Dec 2025	Pending
WP5	Final Conference Proceedings	CU/NCAD/	Other	31 Oct 2025	Pending
WP5	Edited Book	CU/ NCAD	Report	30 Jun 2025	Pending
WP5	Guest Edited Journal Issue	NCAD/CU	Report	31 Dec 2025	Pending
WP6	H - Requirement No. 6	NCAD/CU	Report	31 Dec 2025	Pending
WP6	POPD - Requirement No. 10	UoN	Ethics	30 Apr 2020	Pending

Table 4: Second Period Deliverables

1.9.2 Monthly Work Package Meetings

Work Package Meeting	Date	Time	Description	Presentations
1	3-Oct-23	16:30-17:30 GMT	Introduction Session to Work Package	2/3 5m sharings from completed/started secondments
2	4-Nov-23	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
3	5-Dec-23	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
4	9-Jan-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	ECR Session	Conversation, sharing and feedback session for ECRs
5	6-Feb-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	SR Session	Conversation, sharing and feedback session for SRs
6	5-Mar-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
7	2-Apr-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
8	7-May-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
9	4-Jun-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to SpaceX Conference	Introduction to SpaceX Conference and Work Package contributions
10	2-Jul-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to SpaceX Conference	Call for contributions / panels
11	6-Aug-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to SpaceX Conference	Finalise Contributions
12	3-Sep-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to SpaceX Conference	Work Package proposal sent
13	1-Oct-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to SpaceX Conference	Introduction to Town Hall Event, develop idea for theme.
14	5-Nov-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
15	3-Dec-24	16:30-17:30 GMT	Work Package 2 WIP Session	3-5 5-15m sharings from completed/started secondments. 30m Discussion time around
16	7-Jan-25	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to Town Hall Event	Call for contributions / panels
17	4-Feb-25	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to Town Hall Event	Finalise Contributions
18	4-Mar-25	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to Town Hall Event	Work Package proposal sent
19	4/1/2025	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to Town Hall Event	Work Package proposal sent
20	6-May-25	16:30-17:30 GMT	Looking Forward to Town Hall Event	Work Package proposal sent

Table 5: Work Package Meetings, draft September 2023

1.9.3 SPACE X – RISE Final Conference

A final conference will take place in the UK in June/ July 2025. Work Package meetings will inform the choice of Keynote Speakers, Panels, and the process of Call for Papers.

1.9.4 Town Hall Meetings

Three Town Hall Meetings are planned in Nicosia, CY Vienna, A and Northampton, UK. The aim of the Town Hall events is to raise awareness of the project to wider publics. The events will also enable the sharing of research outputs and findings.

1.9.5 SPACEX- RISE Edited Book

There will a published book contracted by Routledge and edited by Hewitt, Jordan, Mahony and Stratis. The working title is 'Spatial Practices and the Urban Commons', which brings together varied outcomes from the research secondments, training events and the final conference.

2. SPACEX-RISE Research Work Packages

Prof. Mel Jordan

The three research work packages: 1. Practices, 2. Urban Subjects and 3. Archives are designed to group researchers through their current interests and outcomes. The three WP's enable us to explore:

- The way in which art, architecture, and design practices operate in the public realm for community cohesion.
- The way in which pedagogical methods support the transformation of subjects and the formation of communities of interest.
- The way in which the archive can be utilised for recording and documenting spatial projects to support best practice.
- The way cultural policy can be generated from grass-roots activity.

2.1 Person Month Secondments

The PM research secondments have been planned to enable the four research topics within each work package to be addressed. Secondment movement is based on exchanges between researchers where identified research interests and potential for knowledge

exchange occur. This enables the 'twinned' researchers, their organisations, and institutions to develop their research outputs and public events together.

ERs and ESRs allocated to each WP represent specialists from the disciplines included in the action. This allows a range of methods and approaches to operate within each WP and across secondment allocation, resulting in knowledge transfer and a broader engagement with understanding cultural value from all disciplines. Researchers carrying out practice research have been paired with host institutions and where possible and within reason (via agreement on resource implications), access to public and community groups or support the delivery of a public talk/performance event, display of research activity; historical research occurs with institutions that hold archives; pedagogical methods are supported by organisations that have educational practices; urban and public realm work is aligned to third sector organisations enabling access to links already established with local community groups, community leaders and town/city leaders.

2.1.2 SPACEX-RISE Research Questions

The project investigates how 'spatial practice' can produce urban subjects and urban commons where cultural and moral boundaries can be shifted, and conflict can be transformed into civic discourse through agonistic processes of exchange. There is a dynamic interrelation of the WPs through the project's activities (secondments, training sessions, communication, conference, publication, etc). Each Work Package comprises 4 inter-related research topics (RTs)

Overarching Research Question:

How do spatial practices effect public exchange and opinion formation in urban spaces, and enable more empathetic and inclusive ways of living together? (WPs 2, 3 & 4)

Additional Research Questions:

1. How can transdisciplinary and cross-sector research methodologies help us better analyse and understand the role that spatial practices play in re-invigorating democratic processes within civil society? (WP2)
2. In what ways can the new knowledge generated through the SPACEX-RISE action shape future spatial practices as well as cultural and social policy and the practice of urban planning to promote inclusionary practices? (WPs 2 & 3)

3. How do the pedagogic strategies employed by spatial practices effect and contribute to the transformation and construction of subjectivity? What forms of knowledge are produced, and what types of subjects are supported? (WP3)
4. What role does the archive play in understanding how historical and concurrent spatial practices address issues of democratic exchange and conflict? What are the limitations of extant archiving models and how can the archive be reimagined and reconfigured as a common, centralised shared resource? (WP4)

2.1.3 SPACEX-RISE Aims and Objectives

To create new spatial practice projects (art, architecture, and design) in public space, and measure and document how these practices intervene in urban space to promote new and inclusive ways of living together. (WP2)

- To understand how both new and historical spatial practice projects generate an informal approach to producing new subjectivities and enabling community and the commons to thrive. (WP3)
- To analyse historical and concurrent knowledge stored in archives on the role spatial practices play in addressing issues of democratic exchange and conflict resolution. (WP4)
- To create new knowledge that can be utilised to inform and shape future cultural and social policy and the practice of urban planning and the production of empathetic communities (WPs 2 & 3)

2.1.4 Deliverables for WP2, WP3 & WP4

Best Practice Report Fact Sheet will be authored for each Work Package (WP2, D2.1, D4, WP3, D3.1, D7, WP4, D4.1, D10)

The findings from the above these will inform the three Town Hall Meetings, the Final Conference, and the contents of the Routledge Companion to 'Spatial Practice and the Urban Commons'.

3. Work Package 2: Practices

The aim of WP2 is to examine spatial practices and to analyse how they operate for social benefit. The emphasis will be on ways in which art, architecture, and design projects in the public realm impact upon and develop new cultural understandings. RT1: Spatial Practices as Place Making will reflect upon on art, architecture and design projects in urban space; RT2: Mapping Practice-led Urban Thresholds for New Urban Subjects will analyse and report on an ongoing series of projects in relation to urban thresholds; RT3: Interrogating the Role Spatial Practices Play in Conflict Transformation will analyse existing projects in relation to art historical practices and methods to assess and articulate the legacy of spatial practices in conflict resolution; and RT4: Activating Urban Spatial Relations: the Role of Practice in Urban planning and Policy-making will analyse extant spatial practice projects to understand how the methods generated through these projects impact upon the construction of cultural policy, what the relationships are to (other) art infrastructures and how their meanings and use have changed.

3.1 WP2 Research Context

In recent years the demise of public spaces has contributed to the rise in populist nationalism across Europe. Seemingly common spaces such as parks and squares, though publicly accessible, are increasingly privately owned or managed. This restricts the way in which these spaces are used, such as the right to free assembly, and enforces oppressive forms of civic behaviour. Individuals require public forums – arenas of communal interaction where people come together and discuss the deeds of the state and the market – to affect democratic exchange. WP2 enquires into the role played by spatial and social art practices that utilise engagement and encounter in the functioning and maintenance of the democratic exchange of opinion between groups and individuals.

The history of social art practices is located in the history of the avant-garde, with a desire to connect art to everyday life. Social artworks develop out of participatory art processes, which include education methods, dialogue, and discussion: these are now accepted as standard techniques in the production of contemporary artworks and are articulated deriving from an engagement with sites and spaces. Social art practice is associated with an impulse to democratize both art production and society. The artist as producer of deliberation and participation was born out of the radical counter-aesthetics of the 1960s and is evident in community arts' 'new genre public art' in which artists worked with specific social

constituents as well as the Artist Placement Group that believed that 'context was half the work'.

3.2 Practice Research

Practice research is important for disciplines that generate practice as part of their study and enquiry - art, design, and architecture (as well as performing arts). Practice research enquiries are engaged in the histories, practices, and theories of the discipline. Arts and Humanities disciplines have made a strong case for practice research to be an accepted way in which knowledge is generated and shared. This can include knowledge from lived experience as well as innovations in the production of artefacts. Practice research in art, design and architecture has a significant relationship with ideas of publics, audiences, viewers, spectators, readers, and users. Practice-research includes methods such as qualitative data collection, ethnography, and action research. Practice-based research is also used to test ideas, a product can be developed to see how well the user can employ the new idea or how well it works. Also, as an engagement tool to find out things about a community. Practice-led research foregrounds art and design practices and explores how artefacts are produced and why, within a context of art history, philosophy, and social theory etc. Practice research is more than a method - it is an approach. It is embedded in the subject discipline and therefore inherent to enquires in the 'practical/plastic' arts. It is complex because of its interweaving activity incorporating action, argumentation, and reflection resulting in reflexive practice. Artefacts that are produced are not necessarily discrete art objects and included systems and interventions. Practice research supports the importance of other forms of knowledge – lived experience, craft skills, production of events as well as conventional artistic works and it enables us to value practice as one part of knowledge making - which is fundamental to our subject areas. It can enable new communication with others through innovative exchanges (as a type of applied research). It brings practice and theory into a useful encounter with each other to advance collective understanding. For example, this provides an addition to an historian's accounts of artistic practices (lived experience). Finally, it does something in the world - moves things around, creates contingent situations calling on a variety of actors and places things, other creatures, plants, climate and so on in a more central position to humans.

Practice research is very much accepted in the UK government Research Exercise Framework (REF), particularly in Panel UoA32 Art and Design: History, Practice and Theory

and Panel UoA33 Music, Dance, Drama and Performing Arts. PhDs in practice research have been accepted for over 20 years.

Figure 11: Diagram, Smith and Dean, Practice-led Research, Research-led Practice in the Creative Arts, 2009

3.3 WP 2 Secondments - Feedback 1

Dr. Jasper Joseph Lester (RCA) describes completed and ongoing secondments.

Dr. Jaspar Joseph-Lester, secondment with Transparadiso and K. Yoland – Rosa Luxemburg Berlin Secondment.

Figure 12: *The Chemnitz Pavilion*, location-based sticker by Frauke Wetzel, Jasper Joseph-Lester

Figure 13: Hung up to dry, K. Yoland, 2023, in the exhibition <Exit is No Object>, KHSB Berlin-Karlshorst, 2023 © photo: K. Yoland.

Figure 14: Installation view: <Exit is No Object>, KHSB Berlin-Karlshorst, 2023 © photo: Achim Hatziu

3.4 WP 2 Secondments - Feedback 2

Miguel Amado (Sirius) researcher secondments. Georgia Perkins – Secondment to Coventry University, and reflections on hosting researchers at Sirius.

Figure 15: Poster for researcher talk at Coventry University, 2023, designed by James Smith

Figure 16: Earthwise project – Georgia Perkins, creating the publication at the Royal College of Art, 2022

Figure 17: Prof. Christa-Maria Lerm Hayes leading a Sirius Summer School session, 2023

Figure 18: Andy Hewitt and Mel Jordan in conversation with Dr. Eve Olney, (Living Commons) at the opening of 'Talk to the Land', exhibition at Sirius, 2023

Figure 19: Eventbrite promotion. A discussion on social art practice, the production of new works for Talk to the Land (Hewitt and Jordan) and the curation of Brian O'Doherty's work (Lerm Hayes), March 2023

4.2 WP3 Research Contexts

- First Story: The 'Exiled' Subject

Figure 21: Etel Adnan, 'Voyage, Guerre, Exil'

- Second Story: The 'Colonial' Subject

Figure 22: Didier Daeninckx's 'Cannibale' published in 1998

- An Argument: Producing affects for the urban subject

Figure 23: Chantal Mouffe, 'Towards a Green Democratic Revolution- Left Populism and the Power of Affects'

4.3 WP 3 Secondments - Feedback 1

Andri Christofides (H4C) describes ongoing secondments from H4C to Coventry University

Figure 24: Streets of Coventry, 2023, Herbert Museum and Art Gallery, Coventry 2023 images by Andri Christofides

Figure 25: Nicosia 2017, image by Andri Christofides

4.4 WP 3 Secondments - Feedback 2

Dr. Fiona Whelan (NCAD) describes ongoing secondment with H4C

“I have been on two research trips to Home For Cooperation in 2023. I will make one or two more trips in 2024 to complete the 31-day secondment. Focused on work package 3 ‘Urban Subjects’, I have been guided by two research questions while on both trips:

- How do the pedagogic strategies employed by spatial practices effect and contribute to the transformation and construction of subjectivity?
- What forms of knowledge are produced, and what types of subjects are supported?

I am currently working on a series of stories to capture the essence of my research as it addresses the above questions. As an outsider in a new context, city and country I had never been in previously, I feel it is important to first write about the complexity of my own subject position as a SPACEX researcher concerned with the above questions. Working from notes taken during my first two trips, capturing moments when I felt a particular aspect of my own subjectivity was elicited, the first story intends to highlight the relevance and multiplicity of the researcher's positionality. Subsequent stories will deal with my observations of how different aspects of a city's infrastructure can project and enforce specific subjectivities and how I observe specific social and spatial practices and methodologies nurturing new, emergent, and collective subjectivities."

Story 1: Subjectivities elicited in me as a researcher.

Dr. Fiona Whelan, September 2023.

It's January 2023. I am next in line for passport control in Paphos Airport. I can hear the conversation between the uniformed man and the man who was just ahead of me in the queue. His passport looks the same as mine. But there are questions. Where are you from originally? How long will you stay? My turn. No questions. I am white. The bus trip from the airport to Nicosia reveals stunning scenery. The bus travels on the left side of the road. This is not new to me. When I get to the hotel, I need to charge my phone. I do not need the European adaptor I had brought along. The plug socket is not new to me either. I am from a country that was colonised by Britain. It's dark but I'm hungry so I go for a walk to find food. I hear lots of accents, my ear picking up on many languages. I am English speaking. Men gather in groups along the path outside shops, cafés and transport hubs. I feel their eyes. I am a woman. After eating, I head for an evening concert in Home For Cooperation. A local band will play. As I leave the hotel, I ask the receptionist if I need a passport to enter the buffer zone. He tells me to always carry it. I walk along by the old walls and find the crossing point. I can hear the music on the air, reassuring me that I'm going in the right direction. I offer my passport to the uniformed man at the crossing. He gives me permission to proceed. I am an EU citizen. I chat to new people that evening. Some make comparisons between the political realities in Ireland and Cyprus – the complex line that divides each island. Is that

why I chose this place for my SPACEX secondment. Partly. But also because I am drawn to islands. I am an islander. The next day I explore the city on foot. I stop off in cafes for breaks and order tea. I am a customer. I spend time writing in my notebook and watching the world from different vantage points. I am middle class. The streets seem emptier than I expected. I ask a local about it. It's the rain. It rains very little here. People stay home when it rains. I am from Ireland. Walking with my umbrella, I visit museums and galleries and ask questions. People are happy to answer. I am a researcher. I've a terrible sense of direction so google maps is in use on my phone. Google doesn't know about the barbed wire and barrels, so I regularly arrive at a barrier I cannot cross. I am an outsider. I find another way through. With my passport in and out of my bag regularly I traverse the city. I stop regularly to photograph public maps. I arrange meetings with many people who are interesting to me and meet others by chance. I listen intently. I try to make sense of what I'm hearing. I share my new insights from one person to the next, thinking out loud, telling one what another told me. I am a pollinator. Someone asks. What is it exactly that you are interested in knowing. I don't know yet. I'm ok with not knowing. I am an artist. I have no off-the-shelf research methodology. I'm following leads and curiosities in this initial trip. I ask the person serving in the café what I should eat or drink. I ask the bookshop owner what I should read. I enquire. I listen. I converse. I take notes. I think. I read. I observe. I arrange more meetings. I take photos. I take some photos of signs that ask not to be photographed. I am privileged. Although the secondment is 31 days, I can only spend one week here this time. I am a mother. It's March 2023. I'm on my second trip to Nicosia. This time I travel with my family, revisiting some of the sites, reconnecting with some now familiar faces and meeting many new ones. It's warmer this time and I sit with my children in the buffer zone outside the Home Café. We drink pomegranate juice, and they play chess and I listen to some young uniformed men at the next table, chatting in English about the challenges of the job. I am a civilian. I buy postcards and calendars at a small shop. I am a tourist. I meet a friend's uncle who shows us around his neighbourhood and brings us to his home. We talk for hours. I am Irish. I hire a car and head north again through a different crossing to Famagusta. I meet more interesting people. I see inside a church that is a mosque. I am not religious. The staff at Home for Cooperation suggest that I come back for my third trip during their biggest annual event The Buffer Fringe in October. That time of year will never suit to travel as it's the start of my teaching term at NCAD in Dublin. I am an academic. As I leave the buffer zone for the last time on this visit, I see a man I've seen on both trips, walking up and down. I am free. To be continued...

Figure 26: Nicosia January 2023, images, Dr. Fiona Whelan

5. Work Package: 4 Archives

Dr. Emma Mahony

The aim of WP4 is to reimagine the archive as a universal and centralised resource that is accessible to multiple users from community groups, commissioners, planners, and policy writers. The emphasis of WP4 will be on the history and legacy of spatial practices, how they are recorded, documented, and re-accessed through the archive. RT9: Art as a Means for Investigating the Archive will produce new (spatial) practice projects in order to reinvigorate and democratise the use of the archive; RT10: Counter-mapping as Open Source Archives for Transforming Conflicts will activate the archive, taking it on the road to test how it can be reimaged and reconfigured as open source for use in conflict transformation. RT11: Activating and Accessing the Archive will reimagine the archive for multiple users; RT12: Grass Roots Practices: Documentation and the Archive will analyse existing spatial projects in the archive to find ways of articulating art policy and methods through archival materials. WP4 will also include research focused on assessing cultural value which is often measured based on archival research.

5.1 WP4 Research Context

Government policies that emphasize achieving a return on cultural investment – both economic and symbolic – are increasingly shaping the cultural arena across Europe. This discourse dictates that culture can no longer be justified based on its intrinsic values but must produce extrinsic values that can be clearly articulated, quantified, and audited. Consequently, cultural institutions are expected to justify their public subsidies through the

provision of evidence-based reports that include simplistic quantitative data on audience access, attendance, and satisfaction. 'Making Value' examines how alternative and inter and cross-disciplinary strategies of measuring value can be applied to spatial practice. It also explores alternative forms of value that are not measured by the neoliberal value discourse, namely the unruly 'outcomes' and 'affects' the arts produce, anti-values that fail to produce sufficient return, or 'return of the expected type' to be considered an 'asset' to the neoliberal value discourse. This includes how spatial practices effect public exchange and opinion formation, give minority social groups visibility, how they reinvigorate democracy and produce forms of social wealth for the commons.

Figure 27 & 28: Images from Dr. Emma Mahony – secondment at CASCO

The archive plays a key role in assessing the ways in which spatial practices effect short and longer-term public exchange and opinion formation in urban spaces (and how, in turn, they contribute to the assessing of cultural value). WP4 explores the role of the archive plays in understanding how historical and concurrent spatial practices address issues of democratic exchange and conflict transformation. More significantly, it considers how the archive can be reimagined and reconfigured as a bottom up, open-source archive for the urban commons capable of ameliorating social divisions and transforming conflicts.

It is important to acknowledge however that, not unlike most museums, archives have historically been instrumentalized by power as a means of reproducing the status-quo. As Jacques Derrida notes in *Archive Fever*, 'There is no political power without the control of the archive, if not of memory'. It is crucial then, that those counterpublics who are oppressed are in control of the archival process. It is also key that the form these 'counterarchives' take is not dictated by conventional archives. As Michael Warner also points out, a counterpublic is distinguished by its alternative protocols, protocols that tend not to conform to bourgeois conceptions of persuasive 'rational-critical debate' and is more open to other forms of

expression, including the non-textual and the poetic. This is the case because counterpublics seek to highlight, not bracket their differences; they aim to expand and overturn normative hegemonic assumptions and conventions towards their own goals. As the discourses counterpublics disseminate are not limited to the textual but comprise multiple formats, the archives that tell their stories must necessarily be experimental. A useful model to consider in the design is *Contested Fronts: Commoning Practices for Conflict Transformation*, the Cypriot entry to the 15th Venice Biennale of Architecture in 2015 which has been developed by two SPACEX partners in Nicosia, AA&U for Architecture, Art and Urbanism and the University of Cyprus. Contested Fronts operates as an open-source archive for the urban commons focused on conflict transformation in Cyprus. It employs experimental research formats, it is performative and mobile, and emerges and evolves in response to new contexts.

5.2 WP 4 Secondments - Feedback 1

Prof Christa-Maria Lerm Hayes (UVA) describes secondments from UVA.

Figure 29: Exhibition view, Brian O'Doherty: Reading Time, 11 March - 17 June 2023
Produced by Sirius Arts Centre and guest-curated by Prof. Christa-Marie Lerm Hayes.

East Gallery

Like many Irish emigrants, O'Doherty departed Ireland from Cobh. The building Sirius occupies was likely one of the last that he saw. This is the former headquarters of the Royal Cork Yacht Club, designed and built in the 1850s for the Anglo-Irish. A residency here in 1996 gave O'Doherty the opportunity to reflect on his origins and Ireland's social and political divides.

O'Doherty was an avid reader of James Joyce, appreciating his manipulation of time and use of the (expanded) English language. Joyce's literary output, also generated in self-imposed exile, gave O'Doherty a framework to think of home away from home. His iconic installations known as "Rope Drawings" are comments on the unsettling but true-to-life experience of engaging with Joyce's writings, especially *Finnegans Wake* (1939). O'Doherty approached reading it sometimes as disabling and annoying, making him silent, and sometimes as projecting lively, darting lines into the world, as in the "Rope Drawings," but also lines of text.

Figure 30: Excerpt by Christa-Marie Lerm Hayes. from *In Memoriam A Tribute to Brian O'Doherty (1928–2022)* Edited by Brenda Moore-McCann

WP 4 Secondments - Feedback 1

Rosemary Grennan (MDR) describes MDR secondments to date.

Figure 31: 'Participatory planning: Theoretical explorations by Annie Vrychea'. Taken from the archive of Annie Vrychea, Professor in the School of Architecture of the National Technical University (NTUA) of Athens.

Figure 32: 'Archiviare le Contro Culture' - an interdisciplinary event held on 4/07 in the Spacex-Rise project framework, aimed at discussing the cross-contamination between archiving projects and spatial practices inquiry (Urbaner IG)

Figure 33: Planimetry of the 'Villaggio Artigiano' of Modena Ovest (<https://parteciparelademocrazia.it/>)

6. Updates WP5 Dissemination and Exploitation: Communication and Engagement

Prof. Mel Jordan

6.1 WP5 Data Management Plan (DMP)

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is the Deliverable D5.1 (D13). The DMP describes the way in which the consortium will manage the datasets that will emerge from the project, and how best practices in terms of metadata and archiving will be used to ensure that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) for other potential users. Furthermore, the DMP provides information about what datasets the consortium is aiming to preserve and in which format.

The DMP will allow these data to be aligned with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot, for which SPACEX-RISE opted in.

In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016), the objectives of the DMP are:

- To identify the datasets that the project will produce.
- To define how these datasets will be made 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project.
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

Please refer to the DCOP available on the website [here](#) D5.1, D13, Work Package 5 (WP 5)
D5.1 Data Management Plan

6.2 Dissemination Communication and Outreach Plan (DCOP)

The DCOP identifies a strategy for communicating the research outputs, research activity, and knowledge exchange carried out in the project. The DCOP outlines opportunities for dissemination and engagement encouraging beneficiaries to use available means (websites, exhibition programmes, events programmes, and community liaison) to contribute to a DCOP strategy. It provides suggestions and examples and presents the approach that the project will adopt with respect to dissemination of the project findings.

The objectives of the DCOP are:

- To share the research findings that the SPACEX-RISE project identifies
- To reach a range of target audiences, through research outputs and engagement
- To define the ways in which SPACEX-RISE conducts dissemination, communication, and outreach.
- To acknowledge the role of a DCOP in respect of a project where key researchers and organisations are experienced at working in the public realm with audiences, communities, beneficiaries, and stakeholders.

Please refer to the DCOP available on the website [here](#)

D5.1, D13, Work Package 5 (WP 5)

D5.1a Dissemination Communication and Outreach Plan

Figure 34: DMAP & DCOP Reports

7. Communication and Mapping

Chiara Valci Mazzara, on behalf of the beneficiary Rosa-Luxemberg, has develop a system of mapping the organisation’s involvement in the project. (A more detailed account of this process will be included as an appendix in Version 1.1 of this report).

Figure 35: Rosa Luxemburg Mapping, curtesy Chiara Valci Mazzara

8. WP5 - Training Events Updates

8.1 SPACEX-RISE Training Event #1: AN INTRODUCTION TO CULTURAL SOCIOLOGY/ ARTS AND THE URBAN COMMONS: NEW VISIONS FOR THE PHOENIX CITY.

Report by Prof Mel Jordan

Coventry University, June 30 & July 1, 2022. The Coventry based SPACEX-RISE training event consisted of two days of talks and presentations addressing the contexts outlined in the SPACEX-RISE research action. The aim of the two-day event was to review research methods that draw on perspectives across the social sciences and humanities, in order that SPACEX-RISE researchers can devise an approach best suited to their contribution to the SPACEX-RISE action. The first day entitled, 'An introduction to Cultural Sociology', covered traditional ethnographic research, field research and participant observation methods. It introduced researchers to action research (with others), affective methodologies and creative and arts-based methods as well as feminist approaches to new societal challenges. While day one – concerned itself with methods and processes that help to explore the social and cultural contexts of working with others, day two engaged with the institutions and practices of the city. For day two entitled 'Arts and the urban commons: new visions for the phoenix city' we moved out of the university and into the city where we discussed the issues arising from Coventry's year as UK City of Culture. We heard from artists, curators, researchers, and local citizens, that gave us insights into some of the cultural activities that are played out in the city as well as the broader context of arts and culture as a UK government process of regeneration. Questions of agency, function and the depoliticization of arts and culture emerged from the conversations.

Day 1 Speakers included: Dr. Marcus Maloney & Prof. Mel Jordan - convenors (Coventry University), Dr. Jasper Joseph- Lester (Royal College of Art), Dr. Akilah Maxwell (Leicester University), Dr. Andrew Hewitt (University of Northampton), Alex Parry (Coventry University), Marley Treloar (Coventry University) Dr. Saba Hussain (Birmingham University), Dr, Sarah Merry (Ethics - Coventry University), Dr Adrienne Evans (Coventry University). Day 2 speakers included, Duncan Whitley (Local Artist), Ryan Hughes (Coventry Biennial), Diane Dever (Arts organisation), Dan Thompson (Artist). Poster Provocations x 5: includes Melissandre Varin (B.o.o.K), Mahandra Patel, Christine Eade, Kauser Hussain and Dr. Reza Hakiminejad (architect).

Figure 36: Training Event # 1 Poster Presentations

8.2 SPACEX-RISE Training Event #2: CHILDREN, YOUTH AND SOCIAL PARTICIPATION.

Report by Prof. Vittorio Iervese.

Festival dei Popoli, Firenze, 11-12 November 2022. The aim of the event was to review the ways of promoting children's participation in urban space through art and culture. Promoting children's participation means promoting children's choices and rejecting instrumental approaches to the promotion of children's participation that would reduce children's agency. The first morning featured university researchers who will present some approaches and examples of research on the social participation of children and adolescents. The afternoon of the first day will be dedicated to an exploration (in space and time) of the city of Florence with particular attention to the relationship between public space and social life. The second day will be devoted to some examples of participatory practices in the performing and visual arts and in museums. Finally, it will be possible to participate in some of the initiatives of the 63th Festival dei Popoli, in particular some premieres of documentary films with the presence of the directors. Day 1 speakers included: 'From Critical Pedagogy to Promotion of Children's Participation', Prof. Claudio Baraldi – University of Modena and Reggio Emilia; 'Observing Communication with Children' (Prof. Federico Farini – University of Northampton); 'Observing Positioning and Narratives' (Dr. Sara Amadasi – University of Modena and Reggio Emilia) 'Accessibility like a gateway for democracy' - Francesca Merz (President of Cooperativa MARE Laboratorio di Innovazione Sociale), MUS.e – Valentina Zucchi (Florence) Performance and Theatre, *Periferico Festival* – Federica Rocchi

(Amigdala, Modena). Day 2 speakers included, 'DIVE: Diversity in Visual-Essay' – Irene Lucchesi (Philosophy for Children) 'Walking Spectatorship: around film exhibition and placemaking. A SpaceX project' – Giorgia Rizzioli (Coventry University).

Figure 37: Training Event # 2 presentation

8.3 SPACEX-RISE Training Event #3: Behavioural Economics And Commoning Practices; From Cultural Value To Social Wealth.

Report by Dr. Emma Mahony

The third SPACEX- RISE training event took place on 2-3 March 2023. The focus was on behavioural economics and commoning. It is being delivered by SPACEX researchers from the National College of Art & Design (NCAD) in conjunction with the Geary Institute, School of Economics at University College Dublin (UCD) and Project Arts Centre, Dublin.

The programme includes, Basics of Behavioural Economics, by Kevin Denny, World of Work, Cooperative Board Game, designed and hosted by Michelle Browne, Participatory Practices and their Engagement with Urban and Digital Infrastructures and Systems by Dr. Paul O'Neill. Walking Tour of The Liberties led by Seoidín O'Sullivan, and Anthony O'Brien of In Our Shoes Walking Tours. Being Horizontal / Sínte at Project Arts Centre with Sara Greavu. Theories of Commoning. Speakers Prof. Stavros Stavrides and Prof. Gary Hall. Elevenses for the "Hungry Months" with Gareth Kennedy. Commoning as Care Practices in the Community Rosie Lynch, Callan Workhouse Union; Siobhan Geoghegan, Common Ground; Ellie Kisombe, Our Table. Part 2: Artists, Dr. Fiona Whelan, Evelyn Broderick.

Figure 38: Training Event # 3 "Hungry Months" with Gareth Kennedy

Figure 39: Training Event # 3 *Our Table* by Ellie Kisyombe,

9. Town Halls, Conference, and Book

Prof. Mel Jordan

9.1 Town Halls

When: M44-46. Locations: Nicosia, Vienna, Northampton Hosts: H4C, transparadiso, NN
Town Halls are scheduled to take place in M44-M46, after the final conference. Locations:
Nicosia, Vienna, Northampton Hosts: H4C, transparadiso, NN

Conventionally a 'Town Hall' meeting is an opportunity to hear a community's views on a series of public issues, originally a political format, it has recently been adopted by NGOs and community groups to allow stakeholders to congregate and to contribute their views about specific local events and activities. It is not a decision-making forum, rather a place in which exchanges can take place and discussions around shared issues can be conducted. The objective is to communicate the findings of the research project in an accessible and welcoming environment, it will be open to a wider range of engaged publics (from the locale) with specific key community and municipal stakeholders targeted to attend the event. The meetings will encourage accessible debate around key topics identified by the SPACEX-RISE action in break-away group discussions. The meetings last a maximum of 2 hours from welcome refreshments to closing statements. Synopsis of the 3 Research WPs (WP2, 3 & 4) in the form of FACT sheets, marketing material with website details will be available for distribution at the events.

9.2 Conference: Spatial Practice for an Empathetic Society

When: M42 Location: UK Host: UON

The conference is a sector/industry facing dissemination event whose objective is to draw critical attention to the unique Pan-European research findings of SPACEX-RISE and to enable international and European researchers, arts professionals and policy makers to contribute to and build on the debates it generates. The Conference will impact directly upon academics and researchers in the fields of art, architecture, design, visual culture, curatorial studies, sociology, cultural policy, pedagogy, economics, and urban studies. Cultural professionals will draw on this information in the practice of commissioning, producing, and archiving spatial practices. SPACEX-RISE Researchers will be actively encouraged to submit papers based on their research.

9.3 SPACEX-RISE Book

When: M56 Published: Routledge

'Spatial Practices and the Urban Commons' aims to explore the function of spatial practices for society by considering the role they play in unlearning, re-evaluating, and re-imagining new ways to live together. This is to counter the imperatives and values of neoliberalism that seeks to instrumentalize the function of art, design, and architecture. The book aims to address the following questions: How do spatial practices enable empathetic and inclusive ways of living together? How do they affect democratic exchange and opinion formation in urban spaces? How do these various forms of knowledge contribute to our understanding of urban space? How do they contribute to the production of new subjectivities and the urban commons? How can the value of these practices be assessed? What role does the archive play in understanding how spatial practices address these issues? How emancipation takes place, to enable the decolonizing of the archive be reimagined as an open-source resource for conflict transformation? In recognition of the changes the Covid-19 pandemic and its restrictions have brought, it asks what impact has the Covid-19 pandemic had on how bodies can gather in space, now and in the future? Post humanism, non-human actors in the generation of spatial encounters, the digital public sphere and post digital relations are fundamental to our position on spatial practices now.

Ends